

Diagnostic Dilemma in a Salivary Gland Lesion on FNAC: A Case Report**Manjari Kishore¹, Ritu Priya Choudhary², Sarwat Fatma³, Saba Hassan Shah⁴, Divyanshi Govil⁵**¹M.D. Pathology, Associate Professor, Dept. of Pathology, Noida International Institute of Medical Sciences (NIIMS), Noida International University, Greater Noida, UP²M.D. Pathology, Senior Resident, Dept. of Pathology, Kalyan Singh Govt. Medical College, Bulandshahr, U.P.³DNB Pathology, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pathology, Noida International Institute of Medical Sciences (NIIMS), Noida International University, Greater Noida, UP⁴M.D. Pathology, Senior Resident, Dept. of Pathology, Noida International Institute of Medical Sciences (NIIMS), Noida International University, Greater Noida, UP⁵MBBS Final Year Student, Noida International Institute of Medical Sciences (NIIMS), Noida International University, Greater Noida, UP

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Manjari Kishore

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Abstract:

Fine needle aspiration cytology is an easy and quick procedure to make a diagnosis in variety of lesions, especially in differentiating a benign lesion from a malignant one. Histopathology remains the gold standard in making a definitive diagnosis. Warthin's tumor is the second most common benign salivary gland tumor of the major salivary glands. It mostly occurs in the 6th to 7th decade of life. It is more common in male patients (4:1 male: female ratio). It is histologically characterized by bilayered oncocytic epithelium with a lymphoid stroma. Superficial lobe of parotid gland is more commonly affected by warthin's tumor. This case report discusses a case of a 58-year-old patient with warthin's tumor where there was a diagnostic dilemma on cytological evaluation. The diagnosis was confirmed after histopathological examination. This paper highlights a discussion on differentials on cytology in the current case and emphasizes the importance of histopathological examination in the definitive diagnosis of this benign entity.

Keywords: Warthin's Tumor, Benign, Malignant, Pleomorphic Adenoma, FNAC Histopathology.

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Introduction

Warthin's tumour initially identified as a benign neoplasm of the salivary glands and named after the pathologist Aldred Scott Warthin. It is named variously as adenolymphoma, cystadenolymphoma, and papillary cystadenoma lymphomatosum.[1] The most familiar terminology used is "papillary cystadenoma lymphomatosum" since it depicts the typical tissue shape of the tumour. The term "papillary cystadenoma" describes the double-layer epithelium with papillary bumps inside the cystoma, while "lymphomatosum" refers to the surrounding and supporting lymphatic tissues of the tumour. Warthin was the first to provide evidence of this tumour, and since then, it has been widely recognised as Warthin's tumour, a term that is simple to use.

This form of tumour is the second most prevalent type among various benign tumours identified in the salivary glands, following pleomorphic adenoma. It is most commonly found in the parotid

gland, with higher incidence in males. They mostly occur in parotid gland, mostly in superficial lobe of parotid gland; rarely in deep lobe. [2-3] Warthin's tumour most commonly presents as slowly enlarging mass which is mostly asymptomatic. They are firm or fluctuant to palpation. [4] Smoking has been considered as an important risk factor in its association; however, no definitive pathogenesis has been defined for this association. [3-5] The role of Epstein Barr Virus has also been described in the pathogenesis of the disease. [2]

We present a case of Warthin tumor, highlighting the detailed cytological features along with various differentials which should be considered while evaluating a salivary gland lesion.

Case report:

A 58-year-old patient presented to the hospital with a painless swelling on the lower right side of his face for the past five years which was insidious in

onset, gradually increasing in size over a period of 1 year to reach the current size. There was no past history of fever, trismus, parasthesia, discomfort, haemorrhage, or discharge from swelling during the course of enlargement. He had no other comorbidities or any significant personal medical history. His family history was not suggestive of similar complaints. On examination, a solitary, soft, oval, non-tender, immobile swelling below the right ear lobule measuring 2 x 2 cm. Overlying skin had normal temperature with no scars, discolouration, discharging sinus or punctum. No palpable cervical lymph nodes were observed. A provisional diagnosis of benign tumour of salivary gland origin was made based on the patient's medical history and physical examination.

In light of this, the patient was further investigated. Since the patient couldn't afford scintigraphy, ultrasonography was performed instead. The results of the ultrasound examination showed a heterogeneous lesion in the right parotid, measuring 2.77 x 2.64 x 2.07 cm, with a greater number of hypoechogenic areas and a small number of anechoic areas that appeared to be necrosis. An enhanced vascularity within the mass was seen, and there was no evidence of calcification echogenicity in the lesion. The surrounding normal parenchyma tissue surrounded the well-defined lesion. The location and encapsulated nature of the swelling within the

parotid gland were confirmed by this study. Consequently, the final diagnosis was likely Pleomorphic adenoma, a benign hypervascular tumour of the right parotid gland.

For additional assessment, fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) was suggested. The aspirate produced a blood mixed cellular aspirate. The smear under study revealed moderately cellular smear having a monolayered sheets of oncocytic cells with moderate amounts of granular eosinophilic cytoplasm and spherical nuclei and occasional distinct nucleoli over a hemorrhagic background [Figure 1-2]. On the basis of cytological features, two differential diagnoses were suggested (1) oncocytoma and (2) warthin tumor.

As the smears were cellular with nests, sheets & papillaroid fragments comprising of discohesive cells. Cells showed abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm with round nuclei. No necrosis or mitosis were noted in the smears examined [Figure 1-2]. Occasionally we could find lymphoid cells, so our first differential diagnosis was given as oncocytoma on cytology.

Biopsy was advised. Ultimately, the lump was removed by superficial parotidectomy while maintaining aseptic conditions. The specimen was then sent for histological analysis to verify the diagnosis.

Figure 1: Cellular smear showing papillaroid fragments of oncocytic cells along with singly scattered cells [Giemsa, 20X]

Figure 2 A-B: Smears showing high power images of these group of oncocytic cells with round nuclei & abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm [Giemsa, A& B-40X]

On gross examination, the excised mass was found to be a spherical to ovoid mass measuring 3.5 x 2.5 cm x 1cm. External surface was smooth greyish white to tan brown with engorged vessels. Cut surface exuded whitish mucoid substance, and there were solid, homogenous, greyish white with few cystic areas and hemorrhagic spots [Figure 3]. Microscopic examination revealed well circumscribed tumor with papillary architecture [Figure 4-5]. The

papillae were lined by bilayered oncocytic epithelial cells. Surrounding stroma shows dense lymphoid population containing lymphoid follicles with germinal centres [Figure 4-5]. Sections from attached salivary gland mass showed glandular architecture with presence of acini & ducts along with scattered adipocytes [Figure 6]. A definitive diagnosis of Warthin's tumor was made on histopathological examination.

Figure 3: Gross image of the excised tumor mass, cut section of which shows grey-white areas along with mucoid material in tiny cystic spaces

Figure 4 A-B: Sections showing a well circumscribed tumor with papillary architecture & stroma with densely packed lymphoid cells [H&E, A-B: 20X]

Figure 5 A-B: High power image showing bilayered oncocytic epithelium [A, H&E- 40X]; along with dense lymphoid collection in the intervening stroma [B, H&E, 40X]

Figure 6: Section from the adjacent tissue of the tumor mass showing normal glandular parenchyma with acinar cells & adipocytes [H&E, 20X]

Discussion

Warthin's tumour, also known as papillary cystadenoma lymphomatosum, is a benign tumour with a 0.3% incidence of malignant transformation. [6] It accounts for 2% to 15% of all primary epithelial tumours in the parotid gland. Extra-parotid Warthin tumours are extremely rare and can arise in the pre-parotid lymph node, nasopharynx, eyelid, or oral cavity. [7] The risk factors include therapeutic radiation for head and neck cancers, occupational hazards, etc. Warthin's tumour is relatively rare and benign salivary gland neoplasm.

It was first reported by Hildebrand in 1895 as lateral cervical cyst variant. The term "Warthin's tumour" was first described in 1944 by Martin and Ehrlich. [8] Several clinical features associated with Warthin's tumour are age, male sex, smoking. [9] It is most commonly seen as multifocal, located in the inferior pole of parotid. [10] Most of the tumor cases are asymptomatic, with few cases causing slight pain along with tinnitus and shortness of breath.

Cytologically, we considered two differentials, as oncocytoma & warthin's tumor. This was basically due to the presence of sheets of oncocytic cell population on FNAC and lack of lymphoid cells. The detailed cytological features have already been described in the case report section. Only on histopathology, we could find the definitive clue to this diagnosis. Histologically, Warthin tumours have a rich lymphoid stroma and a double layer of oncocytic epithelium with a papillary and cystic architecture. [7] The tumour is surrounded by a thin

capsule. Epithelial component contains two layers of granular, oncocytic columnar or cuboidal cells with papillary projections. They contain epithelial, inflammatory cells and cholesterol clefts. [11] Similarly in our case, the tumour has bilayer oncocytic columnar epithelium, surrounded by lymphoid stroma with germinal centre.

Histological subtypes and phases of Warthin tumour have been described by Steiferts heterotrophic-theory [11-12]:

1. Subtype 1 (classic)-equal proportions of epithelium and connective tissue
2. Subtype 2 (stroma poor)-epithelial component 70-80%,
3. Subtype 3 (stroma rich)-epithelial component 20-30%
4. Subtype 4 (Metaplastic) characterized by extensive squamous metaplasia.

Parotidectomy is the main treatment option for Warthin's tumour. Ultrasound guided ethanol sclerotherapy (UGES) can be considered prior to surgical resection to decrease the complications of parotidectomy. [11] Various non-surgical interventions such as ultrasound-guided percutaneous microwave ablation (MVA) therapy or radiofrequency ablation (RFA) therapy were also available. [12] Warthin's tumour has a recurrence rate of 1 - 15%.10-12

Conclusion

Warthin's tumour mostly occurs in parotid gland and has a benign course, with a very low chance of developing into a malignancy. Surgery is the main

treatment option for Warthin's tumour. It has a very low rate of recurrence.

FNAC is a quick and easy method in giving a clue to this benign etiology.

This also helps in differentiating various differentials as described in detail in the current case report.

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